

**MODERN METHODOLOGY BASED ON EDUCATION AND
UPBRINGING OF STUDENTS IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS**

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Abstract: The establishment of specialized schools in secondary special and general education schools allows to improve the quality in this field of education. Because, in specialized schools, lessons are divided into periods based on the activities and interests of students. A modern methodology program has been launched to make the topics understandable to students. In this program, in order for students to understand the topic, teachers conduct various competitions between groups and perform various questions and answers. In addition to parents, the teacher is responsible for the quality education and upbringing of students in schools. Therefore, it is necessary to form the education and upbringing of the student together. In this article, research on the development of modern methodology for the formation of education and upbringing of students in specialized schools is carried out.

Keywords: Modern methodology, quality education program, education, specialized schools, pedagogy theoretical aspects, pedagogy practical aspects.

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priorities for the development of a modern methodology based on the education and training of students in specialized schools have been determined. In this, the tasks of increasing the activity of students, establishing a quality education program and ensuring that students use their free time effectively were considered. We need to provide students with an active participation in events and contests held at school and by introducing a system of encouraging them, we should form them morally and educationally. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priorities for the development of a modern methodology based on the education and training of students in specialized schools have been determined. In this, the tasks of increasing the activity of students, establishing a quality education program and ensuring that students use their free time effectively were considered. We need to provide

students with an active participation in events and contests held at school and by introducing a system of encouraging them, we should form them morally and educationally. In schools based on specialized education, instructions are given on the preparation of modern methodology based on education and upbringing of students. It consists in increasing students' knowledge and skills, increasing their interest in science. It can be considered as a program for creating the methodology of school education at the stages based on education and upbringing of modern educational models. Qualified pedagogue chemistry teacher Jumamuratov.R. has conducted many studies on the formation of chemistry teaching methodology in schools. The main content and essence of these studies is to create methods on a simple, understandable topic for students in school education. The object of pedagogy is mainly schoolchildren, and the subject is the theory of education given to students and practice. Pedagogy meets the needs of society and the purpose of education learning content depending on the age characteristics of the students requires going, the components of education and they reveals the connections between At the same time, education and upbringing summarizes experiences in the field, the future of education shows the prospects and ways of development. It is known that every teacher-educator and student has his own motherland should know its history well. History of education, pedagogy he can become a teacher without knowing history it's not. For a deeper understanding of the theory of pedagogy he must know the path of development in the past. The teacher-educator educates and educates students has a systematic effect on it. In this he is psychology and based on social factors. In a certain sense, psychology can be included in the system of pedagogical sciences. The theory of education of ethics and aesthetics of pedagogy provides information on the department. This is the behavior and manners of a student defining, setting standards and in a broad sense explanation, aspects of life in the mind of the student evokes affection. Ways of teaching subjects are also part of pedagogy related to the didactics department. It is known that teaching students in various fields and pedagogy of the theoretical and practical aspects of education science itself cannot explain in detail. The science of pedagogy networks are an important factor in positively solving these problems is considered. Currently, pedagogy is divided into several branches. Including general pedagogy (students of school age discusses upbringing and education), before school educational pedagogy (education of preschool children deals with problems), cultural and educational pedagogy (studying the problems of managing cultural and educational activities), military

pedagogy (army captains and students of our homeland education of young people who can effectively use glory, mature fighters in the direction) there are such systems-networks. Pedagogy is the education of only healthy students not only with, but also with the education of disabled children is engaged in. Interdependence of development and education in pedagogy it is one of the most important issues and causes many discussions. Personality development is a long, complex process it is realized through many internal and external influences and factors. As long as a person lives, he grows and matures throughout his life will change. This is especially true in childhood, adolescence and adolescence clearly visible. By development we mean both physical and mental development of a person and we understand the process of spiritual maturity. Pedagogy and biological and social characteristics of the development of psychological sciences as a whole process that is closely related to each other counts. Development of a person as a person, all-round perfection pedagogy in order to achieve the effectiveness of finding laws of scientific development, factors affecting it as well as education and activity in personal development determines and analyzes its impact, significance. During human life undergoes a complex process of development, resulting in a person becomes. Pedagogical requirement is the initial method in the educational process. To encourage certain activities of the student or to stop and show clear practical and human qualities provides. The method of demanding many moral qualities of students helps to form, at the same time in the students is special in developing responsibility and demandingness towards oneself performs the task. Looking at the unified pedagogical requirements, only in our society is the spiritual and political unity of the people pedagogical requirements are effective in strengthening the educational process can become a method. The teacher works with students and organizes their activities as long as it is enough, some actions of the students with their own instructions encourages. To them in the process of educational and educational work makes certain comments, reprimands or encourages, ends. Some of his commands are short and to the point. There are many others, even though it seems like a subtle coercion a broad explanation will take the form of guidelines. Some of them due to the need to engage students only in work, others correction of children's acquisition of certain skills and competencies arose with the need to enter; some of the students others are successful if they stop their unnecessary and wrong actions strengthens and supports actions. The teacher organization of educational and socially useful activities of students without a request it is impossible to imagine. An

experienced pedagogue has a wide program of activities for children goes along with, what each of his students when knows how to do it in a certain way. After all, the requirements for this program is a means of implementation in their work and behavior, only the main types of pedagogical requirements in the process of education and let's look at the forms. The requirements of the teacher can be indirect requirements, in which the teacher expects them to achieve certain actions. The requirements of the teacher are instrumental requirements, in which the teacher children with their demands are next to their friends makes demands. The main goal of education is to form a spiritually developed, intellectually and morally mature person. Accordingly, the content and organizational forms of educational activities and methods are intended to achieve this goal. The main task of the general education school is the mental, moral, emotional and physical development, abilities as favorable conditions as possible for all-round development is to create. Also, students have national pride and nationalism morality involves the formation of manners. Educational work is a continuous and goal-oriented process is a process. Often several goals and tasks at once is done, which often makes the student body intellectual and moral provides growth. A goal and a goal are not the same thing. A good one although the purpose is expressed, but the realization of this purpose no work may have been done for . that is why it is necessary to try to realize a clearly defined goal. The interests of the formation of the person are every pedagogic education get used to common goals, do it systematically and strictly requires an effort to implement at a rapid pace. In youth convincing of the power of the ideas of our society, building a new society to make their own contributions to the development, directly in socially useful work it is important to encourage participation. Turemuratova A., an assistant teacher at the department of pedagogy and psychology at the Karakalpak State University, has been carrying out many studies on the formation of modern methods in the educational process and the enrichment of students' outlook. His researches based on pedagogical and psychological experiences in pedagogy and modern education have been published in many international scientific journals. All the riches of the culture of the Uzbek people, national the heritage and views of our ancestors in the context of tolerance education. Lifestyle and traditions, traditions, norms of the peoples living in Uzbekistan social behavior and moral values should be reflected. Education is key its content includes knowledge about the spiritual life of the Uzbek people should acquire national way of life, understanding and information. In particular, the national education of the Uzbek people has a

special place shows that cultural, social, economic and territorial identity should be distinguished. One of the important aspects of pedagogical and psychological foundations the role of formal education in the formation of personality of national values values are important. Ministry of Public Education Programs and personnel training play a decisive role in conveying national values instilling national values into the materials. Based on this Pedagogy, Psychology, education, or civics or social studies can be done through science questionnaires. Students will have the opportunity to get to know them here with their country's history, political system and cultural heritage. Reading through these subjects, young people gain knowledge about their nation and their identity and values develop a sense of belonging.

Conclusion

In short, the implementation of the program for the development of modern methodology based on education and upbringing of students in specialized schools depends on the knowledge, pedagogical skills and potential of teachers. The main goal and task of the methodology based on education and training is to educate our youth as a perfect generation and a perfect person, to educate them as mature specialists of their profession in the future. It is the duty of teachers to educate our youth in the spirit of love for their country and people. Many opportunities have been created for young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to raise young people to be intelligent, to be able to think freely, to express their opinion freely.

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